

Data Management Plan

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Abstract	In D6.3, we present CONCILIARE data management plan (DMP) for generated (and/or collected) data and metadata. This plan provides specific information about any research/output/tools/instruments needed to store and re-use the data.
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1. Introduction

The guiding concepts, procedures, and standards that govern how CONCILIARE's data and other research outputs are handled are outlined in the Data Management Plan (DMP): "Changing colonial heritage with confidence." CONCILIARE will enable partners, future scholars, institutions, and/or governmental organizations to find, access, understand, and use data. The DMP includes information on the management of research data during and after the project. This covers what data will be collected, processed and protected, in addition to the data that will be generated by the consortium itself. The DMP also contains the policies and standards that will be applied, whether the data will be made open access, and how the data will be preserved.

This DMP is a working document and will be regularly updated as and when is necessary. Project partners will be informed about the changes made to this document within 15 working days. Any comment or modification suggested by consortium members must be resolved –included or dismissed- within an additional 15 working days from its communication to the project coordinator (UC), responsible for WP6: "Coordination and management".

2. Data summary

2.1. Purpose of the data collection and generation

The purpose of the collection and generation of data is to answer research questions linked to CONCILIARE's objectives. The data will be collected to study ongoing changes in Colonial Cultural Heritage (CCH) across six European countries: Belgium, Italy, Portugal and the Netherlands –the four with a direct involvement in Western colonial expansion-, in addition to Croatia and Finland, countries without direct implication in the history of colonialism. The focus will be the colonization of overseas cultures and territories by European countries, not addressing historical processes of internal colonialism within Europe. As stated in the Grant Agreement (GAP-101132582), CONCILIARE has a threefold aim, three Specific Objectives (SO):

-SO1: To identify and analyze **changes** in CCH across four specific domains: **a) textbooks:** changes and evolution of colonial narratives and images; **b) public spaces:** removal, destruction, replacement and resignification of statues, monuments, memorials and street names; **c) museums:** variations in exhibitions, discourses and master narratives; **d) products and traditions:** changes in the consumption of food, customs, souvenirs, social practices and other products or goods related to fashion, pop culture or everyday life.

-SO2: To advance knowledge concerning **reactions** to and **representations** of changes in CCH in different and diverse socio-demographic groups, paying special attention to age, race (self-perceived and assigned), gender, ethnicity, context, religion, occupation, education and cultural backgrounds.

-SO3: To propose four evidence-based methods tailor-made to each domain (one method per domain). To apply these methods across cultural contexts, in order to be able to build and

promote confidence to deal with changes in CCH and reinforcing inter-group dialogue and trust.

Four different Working Packages (WPs) will be responsible for Specific Objectives 1, 2 and 3. Each WP will focus on a particular domain: a) WP1: Textbooks; b) WP2: Public Spaces; c) WP3: Museums; d) WP4: Products and Traditions.

-SO1 will be achieved through in-depth case studies that reconstruct the history of CCH changes over time in six European countries.

-SO2 will be accomplished through empirical approaches on the reception of the changes analyzed in Specific Objective 1. Therefore, it will be achieved through the systematic and comparative analysis of textbooks, public spaces, museums, and products and traditions.

-SO3 will be fulfilled through the design, implementation and testing of the theoretical and empirical tasks performed in order to achieve SO1 and SO2. Four micro scale pilot trials will be carried out in four different European countries to test the four proposed evidence-based methods tailor-made to each domain. Two of the pilot trials will focus on the effectiveness of the methods' hypothesis whilst the other two will address the effectiveness of the application of the methods in fostering confidence in current and future changes in CCH. Accomplishing this objective will enhance potential approaches to CCH enabling citizens to confront ongoing transformations across diverse cultural, geographic, political and socio-economic contexts in Europe.

SO1 and SO2 give shape to **Axis 1**: changes, reactions and representations in CCH. SO3 gives shape to **Axis 2**: promoting confidence in CCH changes. The achievement of SO1, SO2 and SO3 will enable CONCILIARE to expand the comprehension of elements connected to the ongoing changes in CCH. Despite the political, historical and demographic significance of colonialism within European societies, these changes have not yet been sufficiently explored by research. These changes include the contents, structures and dynamics of microsocial representations of colonialism, as well as their relationships with national and other collective identities, in addition to group-based emotions such as guilt, pride or remorse. Finally, by accomplishing SO1, SO2 and SO3, CONCILIARE will be able to identify how these changes, reactions and emotions can be successfully shared by citizens, helping people from different generations and different ethnocultural backgrounds –people with uneven access to power and resources- face current and future social transformations with higher confidence.

2.2. Relation to the objectives of the project

To achieve its scientific goals and objectives, CONCILIARE will adopt an interdisciplinary and multi-methodological approach. The following general terms regarding data management will be followed by the partners in the CONCILIARE consortium:

- a) data accuracy is ethically and academically guaranteed;
- b) data is fairly and lawfully processed;
- c) data is used in accordance with original consent and agreement;

d) relevant national, European and international regulations regarding data protection will be applied.

The consortium includes nine universities and research centers, as well as two non-profit non-academic organizations, each with experts from different fields of the Social Sciences and Humanities, well trained and experienced in interdisciplinary dialogue and collaboration.

-Universities and research centers: a) Universidade de Coimbra (UC); b) Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB); c) Universiteit Utrecht (UU); d) Universidade do Minho (UM); e) Università degli Studi di Roma La Sapienza (SU); f) Archives Generales du Royaume et Archives de l'etat dans Les Provinces (CegeSoma); g) Helsingin Yliopisto (UH); h) Institut Drustvenih Znanosti Ivo Pilar (IPI); i) Centro de Estudos Sociais (CES).

-Other organizations: a) Afropean Project (AP); b) ICOM Belgique Wallonie-Bruxelles (ICOM-BWB).

In both theoretical and methodological terms, data will be analyzed from different scientific disciplines, with special mention for social psychology, responsible for most of the current literature on changes and controversies in Colonial Cultural Heritage (UC, ULB, UM, UU, UH, IPI, SU). CONCILIARE researchers also work in and across other scientific disciplines, such as history (UC, SU, UU, CES, ULB), anthropology (AP), cultural and gender studies (UM), sociology (ULB, CegeSoma), archaeology (ICOMBWB), design studies (SU), tourism experts (ULB) and communication studies (SU, UM), all with extensive expertise in the activities and data analysis foreseen in the project.

2.3. Origin of the data

Data will be collected from project participants, including stakeholders, and minority and majority group members. “Ethnic majorities” refers to people who consider themselves and/or are considered by others as belonging to ethnocultural groups that have lived on the national territory for various generations and represent the largest numerical majority. They are not usually racialized. “Ethnic minorities” stand for people who consider themselves and/or are considered by others as members to ethnocultural groups that migrated or were forcibly displaced –either as exiles, deportees or as part of some diasporic movement- during their lifetime, or who descend from former immigrants of displaced people of previous generations. Members of these minorities are often racialized in derogative terms (see Proposal and EU reports, such as the European Parliament resolution of 19 June 2020; 2020/2685). CONCILIARE focus on minorities originating from overseas territories or societies that were formerly colonized by European countries. Recognizing that there is no correct or definitive form of classifying and labeling people, the consortium believes that racial, ethnic, and gender categories are social constructs that have tangible and measurable social effects.

As CONCILIARE consists of academic and non-academic partners, the sources of data that can be generated and/or reused are heterogeneous. Most partners will use data from scientific publications (literature reviews) or existing big datasets –nine of them already quoted in the Proposal-, whilst non-academic partners, both ICOM Belgique and the Afropean Project, will use structured and

unstructured data generated by their own current or past projects, in addition to data obtained from local communities.

The data generated by CONCILIARE will be of qualitative and quantitative nature. Data collection methods include document and media analysis (videos, audios, images), interviews, focus groups, observational studies, small-scale surveys, and experimental studies. Therefore, data will cover demographic information, interview transcripts, focus group discussions and survey responses.

The reuse of existing data, produced by the body of critical knowledge generated by other scientific and historical endeavors, will be considered secondary data. Secondary data will include the outputs and scientific literature produced by other international projects with direct participation of members of the CONCILIARE consortium. These include, mainly, ECHOES (“European Colonial Heritage Modalities in Entangled Cities”, Funded by EU H2020, Grant ID: 770248; 2018-2021) and the network COST (“Social psychological dynamics of historical representations in the enlarged European Union”; IS1205; 2012-2016), which produced more than 60 scientific publications and involved seven of CONCILIARE’s eleven members: UC, ULB, UU, UM, US, UH and IPI. Secondary data will be combined with primary data to deliver on CONCILIARE objectives. The following is a preliminary list of primary sources for each WP.

-WP1: Textbooks

A) Textual and visual material: historical and contemporary school textbooks from three countries: Italy, Finland and Portugal. Three books per decade will be selected for each country, starting in the 1950s. Books on history, geography, religion, and mother tongue that were written for 15-18-year-old students will be the subjects of the analysis. CONCILIARE will identify and study the chapters dedicated to the colonized and to 19th and 20th centuries colonialism.

B) Audio material: partners in WP1 will conduct 20 thematic interviews in each of the three mentioned countries. As part of CONCILIARE’s intergenerational approach, partners in WP1 will also conduct 30 interviews with parents and grandparents of interviewees from ethnocultural minorities and majorities. WP1 will adopt a social semiotic approach anchored on a multimodal data-driven perspective.

-WP2: Public Spaces

A) Audio-visual material: mapping and contextualization of CCH traces related to public spaces in nine European cities. The cities studied in WP2 are: three European capitals – Rome, Lisbon, Brussels- and two medium size cities in each participating country: Padua and Palermo in Italy, Lagos and Guimarães in Portugal, and Mons and Antwerp in Belgium. For each of the nine cities, two cases –including statues, monuments, public squares and street names- will be studied and analyzed in depth, paying special attention how woman are portrayed and represented. In all cases, partners in WP2 will generate data by taking pictures, recording videos and conducting interviews with stakeholders and key informants, both belonging to the public and private sector (artists, politicians, architects, urban planners, social movements, etc.). They will also collect other texts and audio-visual products such as leaflets and official and touristic promotional or educational publications.

B) Textual material: identification and analysis of archival records linked to the laws, designs, political and institutional procedures required to build a statue, square or monument, as well as to name or rename a street. This analysis will be carried out at the local, regional and national levels. The textual analysis will entail the study of the political, artistic, historiographic and memorial approaches to the designs and projects presented by artists, architects and urban planners. Secondary data will include scientific literature on urban planning, history of architecture, public policy, iconography, “vandalism” and art history of statues, monuments, public spaces, and counter-monumentality.

-WP3: Museums

CONCILIARE will analyze and compare two museums located in two countries: the Africa Museum in Tervuren (Belgium) and the Historical Museum of the Civiltà (Italy)¹.

A) Textual material: analysis of decrees, laws, exhibition scripts, catalogs, archives and all relevant institutional documentation produced by both museums, as well as those produced by ministries and other government agencies linked to them. Partners will also study the colonial origin of their collections (forensic and financial archeology), in addition to the current or potential claims for restitution, reparation and resignification of museum’s narratives and collections. WP3 will focus on how museums respond to the not so recent challenges of decolonization and democratization of the past, without neglecting the more conservative and reactionary movements that oppose these claims and measures, including the restitution of contested objects such as religious artifacts or human remains. Partners will conduct a survey with a sample of 300 participants in each country (Italy and Belgium). Secondary data will include but not be limited to the scientific field internationally known as “museum studies”.

B) Audio(-visual) material: 30 interviews in both countries with key stakeholders, including museum directors, curators and staff involved in the creation, set-up and (potential) transformations performed by each institution. Partners in WP3 will also interview members of steering and advisory committees, as well as decolonial movements and public or private organizations related to the museum’s scope, themes or historical approaches.

C) Audio-visual material: mapping, visual reconstruction and historical contextualization of museum’s narratives, permanent, virtual and temporary exhibitions. This will include the selection of objects displayed and stored, paying particular attention to its narrative framing, the scenography –lighting, aesthetics, positioning, etc.-, and the information or lack of information about objects on display (provenance, actors, agencies, consequences, responsibilities, etc.). Partners will study all the possible itineraries of each museum (in case there is more than one alternative), but also its building and architecture, the spatial semantics surrounding it –monuments, parks, statues, etc.- and its physical and symbolic place in the city. Photos and videos will be taken of all these elements. Through the textual and audio-visual analysis of the Italian and Belgian cases, CONCILIARE will be able to

¹ An amendment to CONCILIARE’S Grant agreement (GAP-101132582) includes the substitution of the Historical Museum of the Carabinieri (which collaboration was deemed impossible) for a second museum equally suited and located in Rome (the Historical Museum of Civiltà).

identify how rigorous, inclusive and collaborative was the process of creation and design of their current narratives and exhibitions. It will also be able to determine how democratic the whole process was, especially considering the relationship between the colonial past and the multicultural present of both societies, composed in part of ethnic, racial and cultural minorities that were victims of and/or were directly connected to the European process of colonial expansion.

-WP4: Products and Traditions

CONCILIARE will study how young people of minority and majority ethnic backgrounds, aged 16 to 30, interpret and construct meanings to the changes in the cultural consumption of products and customs bearing colonial symbolism. Partners will also analyze how these practices are changing and the qualitative degree of these transformations. The countries addressed in WP4 are Italy, Belgium, Croatia and the Netherlands. In each country, CONCILIARE will conduct one in-depth study in relation to a product and one related to a colonial tradition. For example, partners will study reactions to food products with a self-evident and historical colonial connotation, such as the Moretto nougatine in Italy or the Negerzoenen/Negerinntet cookies in Belgium and the Netherlands. They will also analyze traditions of blackface make-up and costumes, including Black Pete in Belgium and the Netherlands, or the case of the Blackamoor [Morčić] souvenirs and carnival costumes in Croatia.

A) Textual, audio and video material: Twelve focus groups will be held in three former colonizing countries: Belgium, Italy and the Netherlands. Four of these focus groups will be composed of ethnic majority members, four of ethnic minorities, and the remaining four will be mixed (ethnic majority and minority members). The four focus groups held in Croatia will be composed only of ethnic majority. The data of these focus groups will be transcribed into text and spreadsheets.

B) Textual material: surveys will be conducted with a sample of 500 people of ethnic majority in all four countries and 500 people of ethnic minorities in three countries (Italy, Belgium and the Netherlands), with 250 participants from each group per experimental condition. Data will be analyzed and compared across different countries and ethnocultural backgrounds with the assistance of NVivo software for qualitative inputs and statistical software for quantitative inputs. Secondary data will include scientific literature on marketing, fashion and cultural studies, semiotics, food studies, and history and sociology of consumption.

2.4. Types and formats of data collected and generated

Table 1: Overview on data types and formats that will be generated or reused in CONCILIARE

Data type	Data format
Text / (T)	Plain Text File (TXT), Word document (DOC and DOCX), Hypertext Markup Language (HTML and HTM), Portable Document Format (PDF), Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet File (XLS, XLSX, CSV), ODT
Image (I)	Joint Photographic Experts Group (JPG or JPEG), Portable Networks Graphic (PNG), Graphics Interchange Format (GIF), Scalable Vector Graphics (SVG), Tagged Image File Format (TIFF or TIF).
Video (V)	Audio Video Interleave (AVI), Moving Picture Experts Group Layer Four (MP4), QuickTime Movie file (MOV).
Audio (A)	MPEG Layer Audio 3 (MP3), MPEG 4 audio (M4A), Waveform audio file (WAV).
Presentation (P)	Power Point Presentation (PPT or PPTX), Google Slide (GSLIDES), Prezi (EXE), Open Document Presentation (ODP), Apple Keynote File (KEY)- all in PDF
Other (O)	For statistical data files, such as survey data from pilot trials and public opinion questionnaires: Comma-Separated Values (CSV), Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet File (XLS and XLSX). For geospatial vector data and other geographic information: Shapefile format (ESRI and other GIS software products).
Physical Objects (PO)	Primary sources rather than “data format”: school textbooks, leaflets, physical pictures, artifacts, displays, collections, memorials, monuments, clothes, fabric, packaging, lighting, architectural designs, etc. A record/inventory of these artifacts, even when the partner does not hold physical possession of it, should be kept in an excel spreadsheet with the main categories uniformized (e.g., author, source, title).

2.5. Expected size of the data

The expected size of the data will vary, but it is anticipated to be in the range of at least **750** gigabytes due to the inclusion of high-resolution video, photo and audio recordings, in addition to extensive archival research datasets. Consortium members should ensure that the amount of data collected is relevant, accurate, not excessive and not redundant. The evolution of data production will be monitored and the storage needs will be revisited and revised if needed.

2.6. Reuse of existing data

CONCILIARE will reuse secondary data where pertinent, such as existing demographic datasets and previously conducted survey data, in addition to relevant academic literature on the topics directly related to the project's scope and objectives, as well as the textbooks (WP 1) and Museum artifacts (WP3). The reuse of existing data will be guided by the principles of efficiency and effectiveness. It will be directed to avoid re-collection of already existing data –to avoid problems associated to redundancy and duplication- and to build on the body of critical academic knowledge generated by other scientific endeavors.

CONCILIARE will reuse the data produced in its research to: a) Achieve SO3: the design of four evidence-based methods tailor-made to each domain; b) The development of Axis 2: promoting confidence in CCH changes; c) Produce dissemination outputs. Both the production of dissemination outputs and the methods directed to promote confidence in CCH will follow the “citizen science” paradigm. This means that CONCILIARE partners will work alongside local artists and people of ethnic minorities from formerly colonized countries, as well as with decolonial activists, institutional and/or organizations managers, and local, regional and national authorities.

-Within **WP1**, partners will reuse the data to produce a small-scale exhibition, a short movie (15 minutes, approx.) and a podcast series of three twelve-minute episodes.

-**WP2** will implement art-based research methodologies, working with local communities to produce a series of audio-visual narratives on public spaces and the history of colonialism. These narratives will address and work with street comics, street photography and street installation projects.

-**WP3** will reuse the data to organize a public seminar with museum's staff and management. They will also conduct two innovative small-scale pilot trials to assess the public's reactions during a customized guided tour in Belgium and a virtual visit in Italy (FACS technique). These two activities will provide new information on how the public appraisees and emotionally react to different ways of displaying and addressing contested information about the history and present consequences of colonialism. For this purpose, additional experimental data will be collected from 150 participants.

-Finally, **WP4** will reuse data obtained in Italy, Belgium, Croatia and the Netherlands to produce a podcast series on cultural consumption changes and different strategies to foster confidence and inter-group trust across majority and minority communities.

Partner US will lead **WP5**: “Dissemination, communication and exploitation”. CONCILIARE results will be available and/or disseminated through additional means:

- a) Conventional physical supports: posters, maps, leaflets, infographics, non-academic articles on newspapers, printed medias and magazines.
- b) Outreach activities: seminars, workshops, training courses.
- c) Academic outputs: international conferences and scientific publications (see below).
- d) Digital media: e-newsletters, articles in online media and blogs, tailored and targeted animations, short videos and digital storytelling disseminated through digital social networks. Several of these outputs will be produced with the technical and professional assistance of MEDIALAB: Visual Arts and Multimedia Production laboratory and the Multimedia Production Laboratory, both based at SU.
- e) Official documentation: infographics, academic and technical reports.
- f) CONCILIARE’s professional and scientific webpage: <https://conciliare.eu/homepage/>. The consortium is still discussing in which other languages, in addition to English, the website will be available.
- g) CONCILIARE’s social media accounts on X, LinkedIn, Facebook and Instagram with publications and updates on the project’s activities, results and related news (including digital versions of outputs and information detailed in point “a”). CONCILIARE already has operational Instagram and LinkedIn profiles. These accounts are showing promising results in terms of presentation of the project (<https://www.instagram.com/conciliare.eu/>; <https://www.linkedin.com/company/conciliareeuropeanproject/>). The website and social media accounts will be available online for at least five years after the end of the project and will be operated and maintained by partner UC, responsible for WP6: “Coordination and management”.

CONCILIARE will encourage the diffusion of knowledge through open-access publications. It will publish at least 20 articles in high-impact peer-reviewed international scientific journals. Partners will also edit a book/monography and two special issues. The consortium has already developed a list of 22 potential scientific journals in which to publish to help increase the visibility of CONCILIARE results (e.g., Political Psychology, Ethnic & Racial Studies, European Journal of Teacher Education, Museum Anthropology, Journal of Postcolonial Studies, see “Proposal”).

CONCILIARE’s results will be presented in international conferences of the fields and disciplines involved in the project: history, anthropology, social psychology, cultural studies, sociology, museology and museum studies, etc. Among the conferences at which the consortium’s results and developments are to be presented include: a) General Meeting of the European Association of Social Psychology; b) International Conference on Memory Studies; c) TAPAS Conference (TAPAS/Thinking About the Past is an interdisciplinary forum for reflection on various relationships with the past); d) International Conference on Social Representations; e) Conference organized by the house of European History and Conferences of the IRAHSSE’s network (International Research Association for History and Social Sciences Education); f) Conference of the AfroEuropeans

Network; g) International Conference of Europeanists; h) Annual conferences of numerous ICOM International Committees, such as the International Committee for Education and Cultural Action.

2.7. Data utility outside of the project

CONCILIARE reaches across macro and especially meso and micro levels of contemporary European societies. Therefore, there is a political and institutional requirement to communicate and provide data access to a variety of external audiences outside the consortium in order to ensure effective data reuse of CONCILIARE's research data.

The data will be useful to researchers studying colonialism, intergroup relations, identity, heritage, democracy, marketing, trauma, cultural consumption, migrations, museums, monumentality, iconography, urban planning and postcolonial memory and transmission. It will also be useful to institutions and organizations involved in formal and informal education, policymakers and advocacy groups focused on minority rights and integration.

The data generated by CONCILIARE will be made available either after or during the project duration. Mapping potential data users with appropriate technical and digital services is important to encourage subsequent use of the data and to support relevant actors can make specific use of CONCILIARE results. Table 2 offers a schematic list of target beneficiaries, in addition to groups, stakeholders and public, private or mixed organizations potentially interested in reusing the data produced by CONCILIARE.

Table 2: Potential users and beneficiaries of CONCILIARE research data, methods, results and innovations

-Scientific community:

-Academia and other researchers working on similar fields: history, psychology, communication, anthropology, museum studies, sociology of consumption, urbanism, gender and memory studies, postcolonialism, educational science, history of art, cultural, food and fashion studies. Local and national research labs and groups. EU and international research centers, journal and publishing houses, in addition to other Horizon Europe scientific projects.

-Policy and decision makers:

-Local, regional and national governments. Official authorities and public administrators. Ministries in charge of cultural heritage, scientific research, social integration/equality and education.

-European policy makers. E.g.: European Commission for Innovation, Research, Culture, Education and Youth; European Commission for Equality; European Commission for Promoting our European Way of Life; European Commission for Values and Transparency; European Commission for Crisis

management and solidarity; European Parliament; European Media Network for Diversity and Intercultural Dialogue.

-Citizens and wider society:

People of different origins and ethnocultural backgrounds, especially considering descendants of colonized groups. People from different communities and belonging to different generations.

-Transnational profit and non-profit organizations with a strong interest in promoting tolerance, social integration and both cultural and intergenerational dialogue (e.g., UNESCO).

-Educational community:

-Formal and informal educational networks and stakeholders, especially those focused on promoting a critical and constructive intercultural dialogue. E.g.: European Association of History Education (EuroClio) or the European School Education Platform.

-Teachers, teachers' associations, school staff and authorities. Students across the entire formal educational system.

-Museums and heritage institutions with colonial collections and exhibitions.

-Museum's staff, guides, curators and cultural mediators.

-Museums, galleries and cultural institutions with a colonial origin or background.

-Networks and international organizations dedicated to the study, professional training and promotion of museums, such as ICOM (International Council of Museums), which is also a partner in CONCILIARE.

-Social workers, professionals, institutions and organizations (public, private, mixed) working with migrants, ethnic minorities and vulnerable people with colonial background.

-Civil society, including NGOs, decolonial activists, artists and performers addressing issues related to colonial memory and heritage (e.g., "Decolonize this place"). Associations for the development of art and urban redesign, as well as youth associations (e.g., European Youth Parliament).

-Cultural institutions and cultural associations:

-NGOs or civil associations representing immigrants, refugees, displaced persons or communities related to diasporic movements.

-NGOs or civil associations fighting against racism, xenophobia and other forms of discrimination.

-NGOs or civil associations representing ethnically majority populations involved in and/or affected by the decolonization process.

-Community managers of social network platforms. Publishing houses, podcasts, radio broadcasts and TV programs focused on culture, heritage, traditions, history and/or education.

-Small, medium and large-sized private companies focused on art, culture, heritage, entertainment, exhibitions, food, fashion and cross-cultural dialogue.

3. FAIR Data

This Data Management Plan ensures that CONCILIARE data is managed responsibly, securely, efficiently, and in compliance with FAIR principles and ethical guidelines.

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

The data used, produced, and suitable for public sharing will be discoverable via DOI and provided with metadata. Metadata will follow the Dublin Core standard using the Extensible Markup Language (XML). A precise and adequate description of the datasets is the prerequisite for identification and thus findability. All data will be assigned unique identifiers and version numbers, also known as “Persistent Identifiers” (PIDs), ensuring detailed descriptions, keywords, and contextual information are included. The data will be identifiable and locatable by using a specific PID: DOI (“Digital Object Identifier”). CONCILIARE will use DOI tags as means of a standard identification mechanism. A DOI is a “Digital Object Identifier” of an item/product, regardless of whether they are a physical –books, artifacts, statues, etc.-, digital –photos, videos, audio recordings, etc.- or abstract/conceptual (institutions, emotions, memories, experiences, etc.). A DOI is a unique number made up of a prefix and a suffix separated by a forward slash: e.g.: 17.4159/135. By using DOIs, both partners and future researchers, institutions or governmental agencies with access to the data used and produced by CONCILIARE will be able to locate and access this information reliably. They will know what data there is, where it is and how to track and locate it.

There is also the additional option to use ROR (“Research Organization Registry”) which includes IDs and metadata for organizations and counting. Registry data is available under CC0 and openly available via a search interface (REST API), and data dump (<https://ror.org/>).

CONCILIARE will use Zenodo as its primary data repository. Partners can rely on additional repositories if necessary (e.g., because of field-specific standard practices or university requirements) or advantageous for the project. In fact, partners are already using different repositories for the deposition of their research data. The following is a selected list of trusted data repositories that will be further explored for use in CONCILIARE: a) Opens Science Framework (OSF, <https://osf.io/> with a server located in the EU); b) FigShare (<https://figshare.com/>); c) Mendeley Data (<https://data.mendeley.com/>); d) DMPonline (<https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/>); e) GitHub and/or GitLab to publish code (<https://github.com/>, <https://gitlab.com/>).

Partner UC, responsible for WP6 (“Coordination and management”), will also use the following public, free and trusted repositories, all linked to the Portuguese national science and research

network: a) Estudo Geral (EG; repository from partner UC; <https://www.uc.pt/openscience>); b) RCAAP (Repositórios Científicos de Acesso Aberto de Portugal; <https://www.rcaap.pt/>)

Physical Objects (OP) –school textbooks, leaflets, packaging, artifacts, photographs, etc.- will be kept at partners' home institutions facilities: libraries, storage rooms or areas especially dedicated to this task. The proper conservation of these objects is of crucial importance for both research and dissemination activities, such as exhibitions or the organization of public-oriented workshops.

Each team is responsible for the adequate custody and conservation of each Physical Object, which must be traceable and locatable at all times. If a partner does not have the resources, facilities or installations for the conservation of one or more objects, it has the obligation to inform the consortium promptly. UC partner and the corresponding WP leader will coordinate possible solutions to this problem.

3.1.1 Provisions for metadata: Metadata will be created for all datasets and stored in Zenodo alongside the primary data. CONCILIARE will collect and structure metadata to enable discovery and reuse of its data. We will use the Dublin core standard, compatible with Zenodo, as a minimal requirement. Any additional metadata will be added in accordance with the specific sub-project's requirements. In this case, the consortium will follow metadata standards that comply with Zenodo. The following list provides a first overview of metadata classifiers that can be assigned to the datasets:

- a) Working Package:
- b) Title/Name: a clear and unique name should be used to identify the data, product or document (60 characters max.).
- c) PID (DOI):
- d) Task:
- e) Type: V (e.g., "Video")
- f) Objective/purpose:
- g) Description (300 words maximum, should include location, participants, context, etc.):
- h) Authors of data product: partner; researcher's (s) name and surname
- i) Date data was produced: DD/MM/YYYY
- j) Data source:
- k) Method of analysis:
- l) Observations (any additional information partners should be aware of):
- m) License/consent (yes/no; which, allocation):
- n) Keywords (between 5 and 7):

CONCILIARE will request partners to ensure that any dataset should be uploaded with a corresponding **metadata** file, following a **naming convention** established for all consortium members, and organized using the TIER 3.0 protocol. A list of "**Keywords**" is planned.

The **metadata** will follow the Dublin Core Convention, unless scientific publishers or the archival platform used for the data requires the use of a specific other standard.

The **naming convention** will make use of the existing structure of CONCILIARE and consist of the following elements:

- Element 1: CONCILIARE
- Element 2: the Work Package number
- Element 3: the task and sub-task letter (if applicable)
- Element 4: the date, ordered by YYYY-MM-DD-HH:MM:SS (with the exact time only being necessary if multiple data files are created within the same day)
- All elements are separated by underscores _

Together, this would give CONCILIARE_3_3a_2024-08-30-11:23:45 for a dataset created for WP3, task 3, subtask a, on August 30 2024 at 11h23 and 45 seconds.

The **TIER 3.0 protocol** is a folder organization system that specifies which type of data file can be found where. As this logic is preserved across all tasks and datasets, it ensures that all users quickly know where to find the information and data they are looking for. It can easily be adapted to the different needs within CONCILIARE, e.g., those partners using secondary data sources or physical objects can describe this in the adequate place and leave the “original data” folder empty.

“**Keywords**” which are suitable for the individual datasets should be decided before January 15th 2025. The consortium will use UNESCO Thesaurus to ensure consistency. “Keywords” should contribute to clearly and precisely identify features and dynamics related to:

- a) sociological factors: gender, age/generation, heritage, majority-minority, socio-economic status, intergroup conflict and social categorizations based on so-called race;
- b) socio-psychological factors: beliefs, difference, identity/identities, alterity, ambivalence, attitudes, group-based emotions and social representations of the past, historical change (or the lack of it), conflict, memory and collective (traumatic) experiences, amongst others.

Keywords will be sensitive and will devote special attention to issues related not only to the ethnic and racial background of the research participants, but also to gender issues, as defined in the Proposal (“Gender dimension in the research content”; Part B, p. 11).

Each partner is responsible for storing and preserving the data related to CONCILIARE in compliance with the protocols of each institution. In the case that the safety, protection and adequate custody of this data is not guaranteed, the partner is bound to inform the consortium to take all the necessary measures.

CONCILIARE will be assisted technically and professionally by a Data Protection Office, based at the partner UC home institution (<https://www.uc.pt/protecao-de-dados-e-informacao-administrativa/quem-somos/>). The consortium will strictly comply with the General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR).

A backup copy of the data used and produced by the consortium will be stored at partner UC repositories, including UC data cloud. A backup copy of the data and metadata produced by CONCILIARE will also be stored on high-capacity storage devices located in partner UC facilities.

The backup copy will be updated quarterly: January 2025, May 2025, September 2025, January 2026, May 2026, September 2026, January 2027.

3.2. Making Data Openly Accessible

All anonymous data will be made openly accessible. Access to personal data that cannot be anonymized will be restricted to members of the consortium unless clearly specified otherwise in the consent form, and with clear indications of the purpose and scope of additional data sharing, with provisions for secure access upon request. All data, outputs and metadata will be immediately accessible unless there is a reasonable motive to restrict its use outside CONCILIARE, such as data including personal data and sensitive information. Data produced from surveys, interviews, trials and observational data will be made accessible for reuse if participants provide written consent prior to their participation. Should total or comprehensive anonymization not be feasible (e.g., in the case of in-depth interview data), the participants' legal right to privacy will take precedence over open access.

Based on each partner's requirements and the data they will collect, CONCILIARE will explore different options to determine restrictions on data use, how access to the data will be provided and how the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained. Data will be accessible under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license, mainly CC-BY, as defined by the Open Knowledge Foundation (<http://opendefinition.org/licenses> and <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/cclicenses/>). The licensing models will be applied to data, code, content, academic and non-academic publications, models, workflows and statistical analysis scripts, including other products and outputs related to dissemination (podcasts, exhibitions, documentaries, etc.). Metadata of official reports and publications will be made open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC0) or equivalent. Several data used in WP1 and WP3 will not be available for secondary research, as they are considered Intellectual Property (IP), with copyrights being held by national ministries, private publishers (textbooks, catalogs) or other entities. In the case of WP1, the metadata will be published in the Finnish Social Science Data Archive's data catalog and publicly available in the data cloud of partner UC. The metadata connected to museums and exhibitions will be publicly available in the data cloud of partner SU, leader of WP3.

Standard data formats will be used to ensure compatibility with common analysis tools. The principles of efficiency, transparency and reproducibility will be followed at all times. CONCILIARE will share digital outputs via Zenodo or another open access repository. Data related to dissemination outputs such as podcasts or short videos will be openly accessible through renowned digital platforms according to its format and target audience. Partner UC, responsible for WP6 ("Coordination and management"), will further determine whether it is necessary to create a data access committee. This evaluation will be conducted in consultation with the consortium and the existing Data Protection Officers.

CONCILIARE will comply with the European Commission open science obligations set out by Horizon Europe. The consortium will provide instant open access to all its scientific publications as preprints under a CC-BY license or equivalent. In order to confirm the publisher submission and open access policy, CONCILIARE will use and rely on platforms such as Sherpa/Romeo

(<https://v2.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/>). In the near future, the consortium will discuss the opportunity to publish their research on the new Open Research Europe publishing platform (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>).

UC partner, in consultation with the rest of the consortium, will decide whether embargo times will be needed for data, outputs and metadata. The embargo can be imposed until M12, M24, M36 or M48 and can be extended up to a period of 5 or 10 years following the completion of the project. After M36, metadata, codebooks, questionnaires, stimulus materials, and a thorough description of the data cleaning procedure that is stored in the trusted repository will be made openly accessible. All these measures will comply and be consistent with national, European, and international legislation on transparency and access to public information. Further to this, partners will clarify which data needs to be closed to the public once data generation has begun.

3.3. Making data interoperable

CONCILIARE partners will use protocols to ensure data and metadata aligns with other datasets related to the project's scope. Data will be stored in standard formats (e.g., .jpg, .txt, .mp4) to ensure interoperability. Controlled vocabularies from the Dublin Core standard and relevant research domain-specific standards will be used. Metadata will comply with international standards (e.g., Dublin Core, ISO 19115 for geospatial data). Standardized vocabularies (e.g., UNESCO Thesaurus) will be used to ensure consistency.

Two different protocols and digital tools can be used to facilitate data interoperability: a) OpenAIRE (<https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/>); b) CESSDA: European social science research protocols (<https://www.cessda.eu/>).

3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

Data will be made available under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license, unless restrictions apply. This will increase output sharing and will contribute to a greater impact of the data and outputs produced by CONCILIARE. Detailed data documentation will be provided to ensure data can be accurately reused, especially for products and activities related to WP5: "Dissemination, communication and exploitation" (podcasts, exhibitions, videos, publications, etc.). For preservation reasons, the reuse of Physical Objects will be limited to research and dissemination activities performed by the consortium. At the formal request of other researchers, social, public and/or academic institutions, access to these objects may be evaluated by CONCILIARE. For this purpose, a specific application form will be developed by partner UC before M36.

Documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data reuse will be provided as soon as relevant datasets are produced. Data will be anonymized where necessary to ensure it can be reused without compromising participant privacy. Data quality will be ensured through rigorous data collection and peer review verification processes, including audits and validation checks performed by partners under the supervision of UC, responsible for WP6: "Coordination and management". These audits and validation checks will take place quarterly, starting in February 2025 and, therefore,

performed again in June 2025, October 2025, February 2025, June 2026, October 2026, February 2027.

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

CONCILIARE will use Zenodo to store, curate and manage data and metadata. As stated above, Zenodo is an open digital repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program. It is free of charge under the CC0 Universal waiver. The costs for the operation of the institutional servers at partners' home institutions are covered by each partner.

Publication costs, either in renowned publishing houses or prestigious international academic journals, can vary widely. Therefore, the consortium and each WP leader will decide the most effective and cost-efficient way to publish the advances and results of the research, favoring its visibility and high impact. As stated in the Proposal, each of the nine scientific partners included in budget two open access peer-reviewed publications in high-ranked journals. In accordance with the EU Commission's open access regulation, no publication in hybrid journals will be funded by CONCILIARE.

Data management will be overseen by partner UC, with support from the IT staff and the Data Protection Officer at its home institution. Partner UC will provide support to individuals and institutions by developing guidelines and, if needed, organizing courses and/or provide relevant tools and infrastructure. Each WP leader will be responsible for ensuring data from their WP is managed according to the DMP. They may or may not appoint a responsible person for the adequate storage and custody of the data at the geographical location of each partner (Brussels, Rome, Helsinki, Zagreb, etc.).

5. DATA SECURITY

Data collected, generated and stored in CONCILIARE will be secured at multiple levels. Data will be stored on secure local servers with regular backups to external servers. "Especial categories" of personal data, formerly known as "sensitive data", will be encrypted. The storage of this data is done on the local servers of the partners who are responsible for data collection and analysis. Access to data will be restricted to authorized personnel only. Detailed access logs will be maintained. Personal and demographic information, as well as other especial categories of personal data, will be anonymized before analysis and sharing.

Anonymized data will be safely stored in Zenodo and in UC facilities for a period of at least 25 years, thus ensuring its long-term conservation and preservation. Within a period no longer than three (3) months after such date, data no longer needed or subject to an established retention period will be deleted. The allocation of resources for long term preservation will be discussed at a later stage of the project.

In exceptional cases where Zenodo cannot be used (either for technical or duly justified reasons), secure file transfer protocols (SFTP) and encrypted email will be implemented for data transfer

(available for most institutional email accounts). In this scenario, access to data will be controlled via password protection and user authentication.

Each partner and WP leader will be responsible for the correct handling and access to data and metadata. Coordination with and between WP leaders will be established to ensure efficient and effective coordination on data security matters. To this end, partners should contact the IT staff, Data Protection Officer and the legal department of their respective institutions. If they do not have access to legal or technical support/assistance, it is their obligation to inform the consortium, especially UC, responsible for WP6 (“Coordination and management”), before November 1st, 2024.

Data will be safely stored in Zenodo and in UC facilities for a period of 25 years after the completion of the project (February 2052). Within a period no longer than three (3) months after such date, data no longer needed or subject to an established retention period will be deleted. CONCILIARE will securely erase the data in their entirety and make sure that they cannot be recovered. Data retained for auditing processes will be stored securely and further processed for those purposes only.

6. ETHICAL ASPECTS

CONCILIARE will conduct research studies with human participants. All data collection will be approved by the corresponding Ethics Committees at each partner’s home institution. Any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data management will be discussed and be further developed in the context of the ethics review being led as part of WP6 (please see Deliverable 22: “Ethics Check Assessment”). CONCILIARE partners will comply with the ethical principles as set out in the Proposal and Grant Agreement.

Groups and individuals who will take part, be involved and participate in interviews, focus groups and guided visit to museums, amongst other data generation activities across WPs 1-4. Participants will be informed about the study’s purpose, procedures, risks and potential benefits in clear and comprehensive language. After a clear verbal explanation, the CONCILIARE collaborator or team member will provide the potential participant with the written consent form and allow sufficient time for the participant to process and understand the information in order to consider whether or not to participate in the research. The informed consent form will include the authorization to collect personal data, to conduct the research, to exploit the data for scientific and dissemination purposes, to store the produced data and to preserve it in the long term. After permitting the potential participant time to read the informed consent form and participant information sheet, the CONCILIARE collaborator or team member will give the potential participant the time and space to address any additional questions or concerns he, she or they might have. If the potential participant decides to join the study, the CONCILIARE collaborator or team member will ensure the participant signs and dates the approved informed consent form. The CONCILIARE collaborator or team member will then provide the participant with a signed copy and keep the original signed copy of the informed consent form in CONCILIARE data repositories.

By signing the informed consent form participants declare that they agree that the CONCILIARE consortium will collect and process their personal data for the purpose of scientific research. Personal data is, e.g., name, birthdate, gender, education, occupation, ethnic background, address

and socio-economic status, as well as combinations of data points that can lead to identification, e.g., gender, age in years, and regionally rare first languages. Whenever possible, demographic data will be collected in the form of categories (e.g., age groups instead of exact date of birth). CONCILIARE will use this personal data for purposes of research, administration and statistical analysis.

At any time, participants can cancel their agreement to participate in this study and/or their agreement to processing their data collected for CONCILIARE. This cancellation will not require any type of justification. The participants will also have the right of correction of erroneous or retraction of personal data by contacting any partner or member of the consortium. The anonymized results produced by CONCILIARE will be published in academic literature – mainly journals, books and book chapters, in addition to official reports addressed to the European Commission - in such a way that no conclusions can be made about individual participants. Partners will take all necessary technical and professional measures to prevent and avoid any possibility of the tracking down of personal information from participants, as well as from researchers, staff and any other collaborator working in or for CONCILIARE.

The consortium will comply with General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 (GDPR) provisions (<https://gdpr-info.eu/>). Collection of personal data, as defined by GDPR, will be avoided as much as possible. CONCILIARE will also comply with other local, national and international laws and ethical guidelines, such as the Declaration of Helsinki. All activities performed and data collected by CONCILIARE will be held in EU countries.

CONCILIARE will specifically work with members of minority groups, including descendants from formerly colonized peoples. Data collection will be conducted in a manner that minimizes potential psychological distress. Especial categories of personal data will be handled with the highest confidentiality. Once again, especial categories of personal data is defined as any information that reveals political opinions, racial or ethnic origin, religious or philosophical beliefs, and health or sex life information. Personal and especial categories of personal data will only be collected if unavoidable. When personal data is collected, appropriate mechanisms will be established to collect, store and use this data safely and securely. Research material will undergo sensitivity reading prior to use to identify any instances of potentially offensive language. This sensitivity read –including audio and visual analyses- will be conducted especially but not exclusively by CONCILIARE researcher who are themselves descendants of formerly colonized peoples.

The same principles apply to products and activities concerning dissemination: podcasts, documentaries, exhibitions, interactive videos, etc. For the collection of images, footage and testimonies, the welfare of all participants will have the highest priority. To respect their interests, they will be active participants in the design of these outputs, and will be heard throughout the production and editing process of the podcasts, videos, short films, etc. When public figures or renowned activists or researchers take part in any CONCILIARE activity or data collection procedure, specific research protocols will be adopted under the supervision of partner UM ethics council. Even though one of CONCILIARE's explicit goals is to mitigate the potential for intergroup conflict between majority and minority groups with origin in former European colonies, the research outputs and results could be misused. To prevent this from happening, partners will systematically contextualize their findings and recommendations.

In order to create data and produce research and dissemination outputs, CONCILIARE, will have to work with underage participants. An “underage participant” is anyone who, both at the time of production of the primary or secondary data, has or had not reached the age of 18. In the absence of certainty about this data or the precise age of the participant, the utmost caution and responsibility will be exercised. The consortium will take all necessary academic and administrative measures regulated by the Ethics Committee of each institution, including obtaining additional consent from parents, guardians, or public institutions, to protect the minor’s privacy legal rights.

7. OTHER ISSUES

Partner UC, in charge of WP6 (“Coordination and management”), holds overall responsibility for the DMP. Detailed documentation will be maintained and stored by partner UC for all data management activities.

At all times, CONCILIARE will follow and comply with national and European “Data Security” regulations, including the Commission Decision (EU, Euratom; 2015/444; March 13th 2015) on the security rules for protecting European Union Classified Information (EUCI).

Potential risks, including data loss or misuse, will be managed by an ad-hoc commission created and coordinated by UC within a maximum of 15 days from the identification of the incident and/or security breach. This “Data Security Committee” will be composed of at least one representative from each partner and/or WP. All necessary measures will be taken to restore confidence in the access and proper preservation of the data within a maximum of additional 15 days from the decisions made by the committee. The Data Security Committee will be assisted by the Data Protection Officer of each partner’s home institution, especially of partner UC, responsible for WP6: “Coordination and management”.

8. CONCLUSION

This DMP ensures that the data generated by CONCILIARE will be managed in compliance with FAIR principles, securely stored, and made accessible for future research and societal benefits. The detailed responsibilities, ethical considerations, and resource allocations outlined will support the project's success and the long-term usability of its data. The DMP ensures data is handled responsibly, ethically, and in a manner that promotes future reuse and accessibility.

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“Good data management and stewardship is not a goal in itself, but rather a pre-condition supporting knowledge discovery and innovation”². The structure of the CONCILIARE DMP follows the structure of the template provided by the EU for Horizon Europe projects. This document is the first version of the CONCILIARE DMP. It will be continuously updated during the course of the project. All CONCILIARE partners are responsible for data generated and for following FAIR and ethical principles. The DMP is designed to meet the consortium academic and technical needs.

² Wilkinson, M. D. *et al.* The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data* 3, 160018; 10.1038/sdata.2016.18 (2016).